

Redox-mediated hybrid zinc-air flow batteries for more resilient integrated power systems - Grant Agreement Number 101115535

Deliverable D1.1 – Website and project logo

Dissemination level

PU – Public	X
SEN – Sensitive; only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)	

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Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Innovation Council. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

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Executive Summary

Deliverable 1.1 Website and project logo describes the ReZilient website, with its content and management procedures and plans for updates, as well as the ReZilient logo and LinkedIn account. Dissemination is an important part of the ReZilient project, and one of the major ways of reaching interested stakeholders and other parties is through a clear, informative and well-maintained website that facilitates easy access to public information regarding the project and its results. A dedicated LinkedIn account helps reach interested audiences, and link further to project activities and results. The project logo is an important measure of visibility and recognizability, to be used in all communications from the project.

1 Background

1.1 Purpose of LinkedIn account, webpage and logo

The ReZilient webpage will give public access to relevant non-IP-sensitive results, items, audio-visual content, deliverables, etc.

The project LinkedIn account, logo and webpage will contribute to the following ReZilient communication and dissemination goals:

- creating a project visual identity and public image
- providing up-to-date information about the project
- sustaining the diffusion of results to the general public
- translating the scientific/technical results into messages for public outreach, comprehensible also by the non-technical audience.

1.2 Maintenance and content creation

The webpage and LinkedIn account will be updated whenever new content is available and approved by the Centre Coordinator. Approvement will depend on the type of content, and relevant partners will be involved in case of potential sensitive content or data. The Coordinator will involve their communication department, who is skilled in both webpage maintenance and content creation and management. All partners are expected to contribute with relevant content. While the web page is intended for long-term content and will be modified to ensure search visibility, the LinkedIn profile will be more for recent updates, with link to the webpage whenever relevant.

1.3 Evaluation and target values

For the ReZilient webpage, the following evaluation and target values has been identified:

- Number of hits
- Country of provenance
- Online visits: Target value 8,000 hits/year from 40 countries

These will be monitored regularly by the Project Coordinator.

2 ReZilient logo

The ReZilient logo is chosen as the name of the project, with the Z emphasized to look like the periodic table symbol of the element Zinc (Zn), which is of crucial importance to the project. The dark green colour is chosen to highlight the potentially low environmental effect of the ReZilient green technology.

3 ReZilient webpage

The ReZilient has established the website with the short url: rezilientproject.eu to serve as the main platform for dissemination and communication measures.

3.1 Content

Figure 1 Snapshot of the ReZilient website

The webpage currently has four sections:

- Home, which describes the overall aim and scientific goal of the project
- Partners, which currently includes all partner logos and link to their home pages
- Objective and Work Packages, describing the overall objectives and work packages in short
- News, where project news will be published whenever ready.

3.2 Website updates

The ReZilient website will be continuously updated with all recent reports, articles, white papers, innovations, blogposts and events, making them easily accessible to stakeholders. The project has a goal of 8000 web-sessions by the end of the project.

It is worth noting that as the website will have more content (e.g. papers, innovations, blogpost, videos) further along.

Figure 2 Snapshot from the ReZilient website

Figure 3 Snapshot from the ReZilient website

4 ReZilient LinkedIn account

The project has a dedicated LinkedIn account (link: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/rezilient-eu-project/>) as LinkedIn has proven itself as the most relevant social media platform in terms of connecting with relevant target groups and disseminating project news. The ReZilient Coordinator and manager has access to the account, and will ensure that relevant and quality assured posts from the ReZilient partners are published. Additionally, partners are encouraged to share project results and news via their own social media channels, as this enables the project to reach a pre-existing audience of relevant stakeholders.

ReZilient EU Project ✓ Følger
3 følgere
14m • 🌐

The ReZilient project has officially begun with our kick-off meeting in Trondheim on October 25-26, 2023.

🔋 Flow batteries hold immense potential for scalable, long-duration energy storage, addressing grid resiliency challenges. To maximize this potential, ReZilient is innovating chemistries and flow system designs, paving the way for efficient and sustainable energy storage solutions.

🎯 Our goal is to bridge the gap between short-term electrochemical energy storage and long-term fuel storage. Join us in this transformative journey as we develop and demonstrate a cutting-edge zinc-air flow battery technology at TRL 4 (lab-scale).

📌 Follow our progress here on LinkedIn to stay updated on ReZilient's pioneering advancements in the world of energy storage!

[Se oversettelse](#)

med Frida Vullum-Bruer og 11 til

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👤 Feire 💬 Kommenter ↻ Legg ut på nytt

Figure 4 Snapshot from the ReZilient LinkedIn page

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